

No pre-treatment differences (24 hr pre; $P > 0.05$) occurred among groups when comparing the number of either small or large follicles (2.95 ± 0.8 vs. 3.02 ± 0.3), respectively. Besides, no post-treatment differences (24 hr post; $P > 0.05$) occurred among groups regarding number of small follicles (GC, 3.0 ± 0.1 ; G54, 2.7 ± 0.1 and G84, 3.0 ± 0.1). Nonetheless, while no differences occurred in number of large follicles between the G54 (7.5 ± 0.9) and G84 (6 ± 0.8) groups at 48 hr post, the GC depicted no large follicle population ($P < 0.05$) 48 hr post (d0). Results suggest that two doses of GnRH in P4-primed goats enhanced follicular growth (i.e. large follicles) during the breeding season.

P111 | Successful vitrification of hybrid (*Bos taurus* ♀ x *Bison bonasus* ♂) embryos

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Wisent (*Bison bonasus*) is a protected species in Europe. One of the latest trends in Wisent protection is the usage of assisted reproductive technologies. Hybrid embryos are a useful model for establishing the methodology of in vitro wisent embryo production and vitrification. The aim of the study was to evaluate the quality of hybrid embryos (*Bos taurus* ♀ x *Bison bonasus* ♂) after vitrification. Cumulus-oocyte complexes (COC) were isolated from cattle (*Bos Taurus*) ovaries and matured in TCM 199 with 10% FBS, 0.02 IU NIH-pFSH/ml, 1 µg/ml β-estradiol, 0.2 mM Na pyruvate, and antibiotics for 24 hr at 38.5°C and 5% CO₂ in humidified air. Sperm from a wisent bull (*Bison bonasus*) had previously been isolated from the epididymis of wisent culled out of reproductive season, and subsequently frozen. Thawed spermatozoa were used for in vitro fertilization of matured COC in TL medium with 6 mg/ml BSA FAF, 0.2 mM sodium pyruvate, 20 µM penicillamine, 10 µM hypotaurine, 1 µM epinephrine, 2 µg/ml heparin and antibiotics. The hybrid embryos were co-cultured with Vero cells into SOF with 10% FBS and antibiotics for 7 days at 38.5°C under 5% CO₂ in humidified air. After 168 hr, only 11 hybrid embryos (4 morulae and 7 early blastocysts out of total 16 embryos obtained (68.75%) and the total oocytes used (21.57%)) were vitrified and thawed according to BOVIPRO Vit-Kit™ procedures. The morphology of vitrified and thawed hybrid embryos was evaluated under microscope based on a modification

of the IETS manual for cattle. After vitrification, all hybrid embryos preserved their good quality (G1 based on modified IETS manual for cattle). In conclusion hybrid embryos (*Bos taurus* ♀ x *Bison bonasus* ♂) can be successfully vitrified using BOVIPRO Vit-Kit™ procedures. Granted OR.271.3.10.2017.

P112 | The impact of environmental factors on the immunohematological parameters of pregnant cows

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The aim was to monitor the immunohematological parameters of cow blood at different stages of pregnancy ($n = 697$ Black-mottled Holstein, milk yield/year 8540 ± 121.64 kg) in environmentally unfavorable conditions (elevated Pb, Cd, Fe, Cu, Zn, Cr) of the Sverdlovsk region for the period 2012–2018. This region is well-known for its intensive heavy metal industry. Hematological parameters were analyzed on an Abacus junior Vet analyzer, and immunological parameters were determined according to generally accepted methods. Anemia was observed in varying degrees of severity, accentuated in the second half of pregnancy: the hemoglobin concentration was 83.50 ± 3.41 g/L. Concerning composition of leukocytes, a shift to an increase in stab neutrophils by 23%, eosinophils and monocytes by 5%, and a shift in segmented neutrophils and lymphocytes to the upper limit of the physiological norm [1]. The number of phagocytic cells amounted to $52.05 \pm 5.04\%$. The relative content of T-lymphocytes decreased to $39.50 \pm 4.15\%$, B-lymphocytes to $25.05 \pm 2.14\%$. T and B lymphocytes were determined by flow cytometry (FacsCanto II, «Becton Dickinson»). The leukocyte-T-lymphocytic index in pregnant cows was in the range of 4.80–7.04 units, which corresponds to the normoergic state and indicates the absence of autoimmune and immunodeficiency states. The recorded changes in red and white blood cells reflect a high level of adaptive reactions to adverse environmental factors during pregnancy. [1] Vasiliev et al., Vet Clin Hematol: A training Manual, 2015.

P113 | Polymerase chain reaction in diagnostics of latent and persistent forms of infectious cattle diseases

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PCR was carried out as a diagnosis of biological and pathological material from cattle, from 17 farms located in the Ural region. We studied biological samples from cows with a decreased milk

production against the background of the absence of clinical symptoms of infectious diseases. Samples of organs from aborted calves and from cattle with suspected infections, negative for ELISA and bacteriological examinations were analyzed. For the period 2016–2019 we examined 830 samples by PCR to identify DNA of BVD, BHV 1, *Chlamydophila abortus*, *Chlamydophila pecorum*, *Mycoplasma* spp., *M. bovis*. Genetic material of these pathogens has been identified in 5.4% of the biosamples. In 1.0% of the biological samples (placenta from aborted cows, organs from aborted fetuses), a specific DNA fragment of BHV 1 was detected. Results confirmed the presence of a persistent genital form of infectious rhinotracheitis in the examined animals. BVD DNA was isolated in 1.0% of the biological samples of stud bulls' semen, placenta from aborted cows and organs from aborted fetuses, which made it possible to identify virus-bearing animals with a latent form of BVD infection. *Mycoplasma* spp. was diagnosed in 2.4% of the cases: 4 samples of *M. bovis* were found in the cows' vaginal mucosa, which is a sign of a chronic inflammatory disease of the reproductive organs. *C. pecorum* was diagnosed in lavages of the cows' cervical canal and in 1.0% of lavages of newborn calves' conjunctiva. The PCR method allowed to identify the etiological agent in latent and persistent infections. Results of these studies made it possible to timely initiate a treatment and take prophylactic measures in cattle populations of the examined farms.

P114 | Hypothesis about the cyclic lability of prooxidant-antioxidant homeostasis in sows

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This study was conducted to determine the peculiarities of the formation of prooxidant-antioxidant homeostasis in cyclical and pregnancy gilts. In the experiment, pigs of the Poltava Meaty breed were used. Blood sampling to test erythrocyte resistance was carried out at different periods of the reproductive cycle: luteal phase, estrus, at 15, 20, 30, 60, 90, 104, 113 days of pregnancy and 12 hr after farrowing. The results show that in blood of pigs during the period of estrus the processes of peroxide oxidation slightly accelerate. During the implantation period (15–20 days of pregnancy) the intensity of peroxide oxidation reaches maximum values as the activity of xanthine oxidase ($P < 0.05$) increases, the content of diene conjugates ($P < 0.05$) and TBA-active compounds ($P < 0.05$) increases. These changes are accompanied by an increase in the level of antioxidant protection, the activity of superoxide dismutase ($P < 0.05$) and catalase ($P < 0.05$), the amount of vitamin A and vitamin E. It was found that in pigs before delivery, there was a shift of prooxidant-antioxidant homeostasis in the direction of peroxidation intensification, namely due to the increase of xanthine oxidase activity ($P < 0.05$). These changes are due to an increase in the concentration of diene conjugates and TBA-active compounds ($P < 0.05$) and a decrease in the content of low molecular weight antioxidants: reduced glutathione, vitamin A and E. The obtained results of

researches allow to formulate a hypothesis about the cyclic lability of prooxidant-antioxidant homeostasis in blood of gilts, the changes of which coincide with the critical periods of the development of pregnancy. Adequate vitamin supplementation (A, E) might reduce embryonic mortality through improved prooxidant-antioxidant homeostasis.

P115 | The effect of injection of recombinant bovine interferon-tau on hormonal and cytokine status indicators and the performance of insemination of cows

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The aim of this research was to study the effect of recombinant (*r*) bovine interferon-tau (IFNT) on blood levels of progesterone (P4), proinflammatory cytokines (IL-2, TNF α , IFN γ) and rate of successful insemination in cows. $N = 115$ Holstein-Friesian cows were included. R IFNT was injected 3 times on days 12, 14, 16 after insemination in doses of 50.000 IU/ml ($n = 62$, Gr. I). $N = 53$ cows served as untreated control (Gr. II). Blood samples were obtained from 16 cows (8 in each group) on days 8–9, 15–16 (implantation), 32–33 (placentation) after insemination. Serum concentration of P4 was determined by IEA with "NVO Immunofan" (Russia) test system, cytokines with species-specific test systems Bovine Elisa Kit (Cloud-Clone Corp., USA). P4 content in animals of Gr. II on days 8–9 was 4.79 ± 0.11 ng/ml, during days 15–16 it was 8.3 ± 0.38 ng/ml, during days 32–33 it was 13.7 ± 0.78 ng/ml; IFNT 304.3 ± 16.8 , 1098.2 ± 62.1 , 673.1 ± 40.6 pg/ml, respectively; TNF α 473.6 ± 21.7 , 341.6 ± 16.8 & 275.0 ± 13.7 pg/ml; IFN γ 1528.3 ± 83.4 , 738.0 ± 48.0 & 745.0 ± 42.7 pg/ml; IL-2 74.9 ± 3.8 , 57.9 ± 3.2 & 51.1 ± 3.7 pg/ml. P4 levels in Gr. I during these periods exceeded the values of control cows in Gr. II by 10.2% (5.28 ± 0.19 ng/ml), 21.5% (10.0 ± 0.42 ng/ml) and 35.7% (18.6 ± 0.91 ng/ml, $P < 0.01$), IFNT by 6.6% (324.3 ± 10.2 pg/ml), 36.9% (1503.4 ± 81.6 pg/ml, $P < 0.01$) and 15.8% (779.5 ± 51.3 pg/ml), TNF α was lower by 3.6% (456.7 ± 18.2 pg/ml), 21.7% (267.5 ± 12.8 pg/ml) and 24.0% (209.0 ± 11.3 pg/ml, $P < 0.05$), IFN γ by 4.2% (1464.6 ± 103.3 pg/ml), 28.5% (527.7 ± 31.5 pg/ml, $P < 0.01$) and 57.0% (320.3 ± 20.1 pg/ml, $P < 0.001$) & IL-2 during placentation by 24.5% (38.6 ± 2.4 pg/ml, $P < 0.05$). R IFNT had an inhibitory effect on proinflammatory cytokines, therefore, supporting pregnancy. The percentage of cows pregnant in Gr. I was 74.1% vs 37.8% in Gr. II.